

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EFFECTIVE SURVIVAL OF DENTAL IMPLANTS WITH EARLY FUNCTIONAL LOADING

Aliyev V.

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine,
Department of Dentistry Faculty of Medicine, teacher
Nakhchivan State University
Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan*

Ashrafov D.

Department of Orthopedic Dentistry, Assistant

Najafova T.

*Department of oral and maxifacial surgery, Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

Currently, more and more specialists worldwide are using dental implants to treat patients with missing teeth [7]. Along with the increasing share of dental implantology in the structure of dental care for patients with partial or complete tooth loss, the requirements for the quality of implantation are becoming stricter [5]. According to current perspectives, the key directions for the development of dental implantology include reducing treatment and rehabilitation times, minimizing trauma during implant placement, lowering implantation risks, and increasing the lifespan of implants.

Keywords: dental implantation, osseointegration, coating, functional loading.

One of the most promising techniques that aligns with these requirements is the use of early functional loading (EFL) protocols [8]. Unlike the classic delayed loading method, which involves two stages, the EFL method allows for the placement of a prosthesis on dental implants earlier than the traditional healing period, which typically lasts 3 to 6 months [10]. This leads to obvious advantages of the EFL protocol—significant reduction in treatment times, less postoperative limitations in the first weeks after the procedure, and a decrease in the number of traumatic procedures [1]. Moreover, implant biomechanics research has shown that proper distribution of the acting force direction contributes to faster osseointegration processes and increases the long-term survival of the implant [4].

The effectiveness of the EFL protocol and its clinical advantages over the traditional delayed loading method have been studied in separate experimental and clinical research. In the study by A.A. Nikitin and co-authors, a retrospective analysis was conducted on the clinical success of 274 dental implants in 137 patients with varying degrees of alveolar ridge atrophy. Of the total number of implants placed, 65.33% were placed using the EFL protocol, while 34.67% were placed using the standard two-stage clinical protocol. The authors found no significant differences in the clinical success of dental implants placed using early and delayed loading protocols in patients with sufficient alveolar bone volume. The study also noted increased patient satisfaction with the reduced treatment time when using the EFL protocol [3]. In P. Mura's study, after applying the EFL protocol in 48 patients (79 implants), the 5-year implant survival rate was 100%, and the average bone loss was 0.56 mm [9]. In the study by A. Pozzi and co-authors, 148 NobelReplace implants were used, 67 of which were placed in post-extraction sockets, and 81 were placed in already healed sites. The

overall success rate was 99.3%. The average bone loss 2 years after implantation in post-extraction sites was 0.69 ± 0.75 mm, while in healed sites, it was 0.62 ± 0.80 mm (the difference was statistically insignificant) [2]. Another study found no significant difference in the stability of BoneTrust plus dental implants placed in the socket of an extracted tooth with immediate loading using temporary non-removable prostheses compared to delayed loading [6]. Similarly, C.L. Tatum and co-authors showed that when following the proposed treatment protocol, there were no significant differences in implantation outcomes according to the EFL protocol in patients with different soft tissue phenotypes [3,5]. Literature also provides data suggesting that early loading contributes to a more successful osseointegration process. In L. Guida's study, the bone-to-implant contact ratio for delayed and early loading protocols was $58 \pm 4\%$ and $52 \pm 3.2\%$, respectively. However, in implants with early loading, a more compact, mature bone with numerous remodeling areas was found, whereas the bone surrounding implants without loading consisted of only thin bone trabeculae [4]. G.E. Romanos and co-authors, in an experimental study on monkeys, did not find significant differences between implants with early and delayed loading, but the authors noted significantly better ossification around implants in the early loading group [2].

Since, according to the EFL protocol, the pressure on the implants in this case is balanced only by the strength created during their installation, the main challenge of applying the EFL protocol is ensuring primary stability of the implant, the lack of which can lead to bone tissue resorption and implant failure [6, 8]. In addition to individual patient characteristics, primary stability depends on the geometry of the implant, its topography, as well as osteotomy protocols that regulate the stress applied to the bone tissue near the implant.

Therefore, choosing the optimal shape and size of the implant is also an important task when planning surgical dental operations [1].

Objective: To improve the effectiveness of dental implantation with early functional loading by selecting the optimal shape of various types of intraosseous implants based on clinical and radiological assessment of the bone tissue response.

Materials and Methods: To assess the effectiveness of the EFL protocol, a single-center study was conducted with 60 participants (42 women and 18 men, mean age 42.3 ± 1.5 years). The study was carried out at the Department of Clinical and Experimental Implantology of the Central Research Institute of Stomatology and Maxillofacial Surgery. The observation period was 2 years. The indication for using the EFL protocol was the presence of defects in the dental arches in the distal regions of the jaws in the molar and premolar areas.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Type I or II bone quality according to the U. Lekholm and G. Zarb classification (1985);
- Single, terminal, or included defects in the upper or lower jaw in the premolar or molar areas;
- Availability of patients for follow-up visits for 2 years after dental implantation.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Previously altered bone tissue in the planned implantation area;
- Chronic generalized periodontitis in the acute phase;
- Bruxism or hypertonia of the masticatory muscles;
- Oncological diseases with a history of less than 5 years;
- Radiation or chemotherapy.

The study excluded individuals with systemic connective tissue diseases, acute infections, inflammatory and autoimmune diseases of the oral cavity, diabetes, polyvalent allergies, pregnant or breastfeeding women, or those who have taken or are currently taking immunosuppressants, bisphosphonates, or high doses of corticosteroids.

Before implant installation, all patients underwent a thorough clinical, radiological, and laboratory examination. Clinical examination included standard procedures such as medical history collection, oral cavity inspection for filled and/or carious teeth, and checking for orthodontic structures. The Green-Vermillion hygiene index and the Muehlmann bleeding index in the Cowell modification were also measured. At this stage, the clinical width of the alveolar ridge was determined. A panoramic dental X-ray (orthopantomogram) was used to assess the functional state of the temporomandibular joint and periodontal tissues. A computed tomography (CT) scan was performed to evaluate the bone tissue condition at the planned implantation site and adjacent structures.

Patients were then divided into 3 groups based on the brand of implants used:

- Group I: Thommen Medical (Switzerland), 27 (45%) patients;
- Group II: AstraTech (Sweden), 26 (43%) patients;

- Group III: Conmet (Russia), 7 (12%) patients.

The male-to-female ratio was similar in all three groups. The total ratio of cylindrical to conical intraosseous implants was 52:48. The diameter and length of dental implants were consistent across the brands. The median implant length for the Thommen Medical system was 11 mm, for AstraTech it was 9 mm, and for Conmet, it was 10 mm, with an overall group median of 9.5 mm. The average diameter of the gingiva former was 4.75 ± 0.13 mm, and its length was 4.52 ± 0.17 mm. Implantation beds were prepared using implant system drills, and a pin was placed in the bed. Next, the gingiva former corresponding to the implant diameter was installed, and the wound was sutured. Sutures were removed on the 7th to 10th day.

Primary implant stability was assessed using the "torque-out" test (load applied by torque) and the Osstell ISQ frequency-resonance analyzer. Implant stability was recorded in relative units of implant stability quotient (ISQ). Differential cutoff points for ISQ, torque, and torque/ISQ values were determined using ROC analysis, which helped assess the risk of implant rejection during surgery.

On the 21st day after surgery, under local anesthesia, a temporary abutment was installed, and a temporary crown made from Luxatemp (Germany) was placed. Afterward, targeted dental radiography or an orthopantomogram was performed to evaluate the initial treatment outcome. Permanent crowns were placed 3 months post-surgery. The odds ratio (OR) was used as a risk assessment indicator to show how many times the likelihood of an adverse outcome in the study group is higher (or lower) compared to the control group (A/B)/(C/D). An OR of 0 to 1 indicates a decrease in risk, above 1 indicates an increase in risk, and an OR of 1 indicates no effect. Multivariate models were built using multiple logistic regression, with coefficients calculated by the Newton method. The significance level (p-value) for all statistical procedures was set at 0.05.

Results: At the end of the observation period, the overall implant survival rate was 97.8%. Primary stability was absent in 8.3% of patients. Of these, 4 out of 5 cases were related to AstraTech implants, and 1 to Conmet implants. Inflammatory changes, such as peri-implantitis and mucositis, were observed in 2 patients with Thommen implants. The overall rate of unsatisfactory results related to functional loading was 16.7% (10 patients): 7.4% in Group I due to inflammatory complications, 26.9% in Group II due to the lack of primary stability and implant failure in the long-term period, and 14.3% in Group III due to lack of primary stability. Immediately after implantation, torque parameters were similar across groups, with an average of 34.1 ± 1.0 N·cm, showing no statistically significant differences in multiple or pairwise comparisons.

ISQ revealed differences in primary stability. Overall, the ISQ during surgery was 74.5 ± 0.9 . In Group III, the average ISQ was 69.0 ± 0.8 , significantly lower ($p=0.004$) than in Group I (75.6 ± 0.70) and Group II (75.0 ± 1.9). Thus, primary stability was higher for Thommen Medical ($p=0.0045$) and AstraTech ($p=0.005$) compared to Conmet.

By the 21st day post-surgery, stability decreased due to dynamic bone formation and resorption in the implant area. ISQ decreased from 74.5 ± 0.9 to 71.0 ± 0.4 , but 3-4 months after surgery, due to osseointegration, it increased to 76.7 ± 0.7 . Statistically significant decreases in ISQ were observed in Group I (by 6.1%) and Group II (by 4.3%), while only a slight decrease occurred in Group III. After 3-4 months, ISQ in Group I returned to baseline, while in Group II and Group III, it exceeded the initial value by 6% and 6.2%, respectively. The lowest ISQ of 68.6 ± 0.20 was observed in patients with Conmet implants. Primary stability was higher in both cylindrical and conical implants placed in the lower jaw compared to the upper jaw ($p=0.002$). Conical implants showed higher primary stability than cylindrical intraosseous implants in both jaws ($p=0.03$).

Therefore, cylindrical implants on the lower jaw provided a greater opportunity for the successful application of the EFL protocol with a lower risk of complications. In contrast, cylindrical implants on the upper jaw showed the lowest primary stability, indicating their vulnerability in the EFL protocol. Additionally, it should be noted that one AstraTech implant was lost despite good initial stability. This implant was a short implant, measuring 4.0×6 mm. Another short implant (Thommen, 4.0×6.5 mm), despite stable clinical conditions, experienced significant exposure of half its length due to bone tissue resorption around it.

In patients with subsequent unfavorable treatment outcomes in the form of complications, the postoperative values of ISQ, torque (torque test), and torque/ISQ were initially lower compared to those with successful osseointegration. When ISQ was below 68, with diagnostic sensitivity of 61% and specificity of 100%, there was a high risk of adverse outcomes. When the torque value was less than 27 N·cm, with diagnostic sensitivity of 80% and specificity of 90%, this indicated a high risk of implant rejection. For the torque/ISQ ratio, the critical level was 36.9%. A decrease in this ratio to less than 36.9%, with diagnostic sensitivity of 80% and specificity of 92%, indicated a high risk of adverse implantation outcomes.

Earlier studies of implant surfaces revealed that Conmet implants had the least structured surface, while differences in the topography of implants from the other two systems did not allow for clear conclusions about the advantages of one over the other. AstraTech implants showed the best results compared to the others, while Conmet implants showed the worst results. However, the magnitude of these differences did not exceed 10%, which is not critical from a practical point of view.

Among patients who received Thommen dental implants, no cases of primary instability were observed. The percentage of patients with no primary stability in Group II was 15.4%, while in Group III, it was 14.3%. The absence of primary stability in the three subgroups differed significantly.

Based on the results of the study, we also developed a method for predicting implant rejection based on the initial characteristics of their primary stability using a dynamometric key during surgery and frequency- or magnetic-resonance analysis immediately

after the operation. In the overall clinical group, only one implant was lost on the 53rd day, mucositis was observed in two clinical cases, and in other cases, the required primary stability was not achieved, and treatment was carried out according to the standard two-stage protocol. All other implants were functionally loaded on the 21st day.

The impact of risk factors, including implant length, brand, form, as well as patient gender and age, on the probability of complications and the absence of primary implant stability at different time points was studied using logistic regression and odds ratio calculations. The results revealed that the stability of the implant at the 21st day and the 3rd month after surgery was statistically significantly influenced by the stability in previous measurements (ISQ) and the bone tissue density measured during implant insertion (torque test value).

Discussion:

The study we conducted confirms the effectiveness of early functional loading in dental implantation. The overall implant survival rate was 97.8%, which aligns with literature data and is considered a good indicator for dental implantation. According to our findings, for patients with Type I and II bone tissue, early functional loading is possible for implants of all three systems. However, ThommenMedical and AstraTech implants are preferred based on the evaluation of primary stability after surgery.

Primary stability of implants placed in the upper jaw was lower compared to the lower jaw due to the anatomical features of the jaw. When choosing between cylindrical and conical implants, many authors, when using early functional loading protocols, prefer the latter, as they are better suited for this protocol, and their effectiveness in such cases typically reaches 95%. In our study, conical implants performed better in the upper jaw, while cylindrical implants showed more favorable ISQ dynamics on the lower jaw compared to conical ones. However, the primary factors determining implant stability are the density and structure of the bone tissue.

The study also demonstrated that the early functional loading protocol is not suitable for short implants, which is partly confirmed by other authors. The stability and outcomes of implantation were not influenced by patient age, implant length, brand, or type, indicating that AstraTech, Thommen, and Conmet implants can all be equally used in early functional loading protocols. The primary stability of the studied implants was sufficient for further osseointegration and implant survival.

Results:

According to our research, the dynamics of periodontal status and bone tissue condition around the implants under early functional loading were favorable both overall among all patients and considering the implant systems used. Bone resorption was more pronounced after 1 year of implant function, although large areas of radiolucency around the implants were generally absent. Resorption was mild to moderate. The high primary stability of the dental implants in the studied systems was ensured by their mechanical properties.

Our X-ray energy dispersive spectroscopy revealed that the surface of implants from leading global systems such as AstraTech and Thommen consists of pure titanium or its oxide, characterized by a high level of microstructure with varying degrees of order. In both cases, clinical studies indicated high effectiveness for both standard implantation and implantation with early functional loading (RФH). This suggests that deep-level microstructuring plays a special role in this process.

Thommen implants do not have a titanium oxide surface but come with a special liquid to increase hydrophilicity. The analysis of this liquid revealed a high concentration of cations, which prevents a definitive conclusion about the causes of its hydrophilic properties. The Conmet implant lacks such high structural organization and contains carbon compounds and traces of other metals on its surface, which may result from chemical treatment. It can be concluded that surface microstructuring plays a leading role in ensuring osseointegration of the implant.

Conclusions:

- Implants of different systems, both conical and cylindrical, are equally suitable for early functional loading protocols.
- The overall survival rate of the implanted structures was 97.8%.
- Conical implants are preferred for the upper jaw, while cylindrical implants are better for the lower jaw.
- Short implants (less than 8 mm) do not provide effective survival of dental implants under early functional loading.

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